

ACCESS Output Data Specifications

ACCESS-NRI

v.0.2.1

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1. ACCESS Output Data Specifications

This document provides an overview of the data specifications for data produced by ACCESS models. The initial draft of this specification targets ESM1.6 and will be expanded to other ACCESS models in time. This version of the specification is intended to be relatively lightweight, as a first step towards the standardisations of data produced by the ACCESS ecosystem. The goal of this specification is to provide a consistent and uniform experience for users across all ACCESS models by enabling the embedding of established community conventions and defined data specifications directly in the ACCESS software and release processes.

Included here are file and directory naming conventions, variable conventions, and variable and global attributes.

More information on the ACCESS models can be found [here](#). Please direct any issues, feedback or queries on the data specification to data.access.nri@anu.edu.au.

1.1 Directory and Filename

1.1.1 Directory Structure

The directory structure for ACCESS-ESM1.6 data output is still being finalised. The current draft has the following structure under the current working directory:

```
<run>/output<xxx>/<realm>/<filename.nc>
```

1.1.2 File naming

ACCESS-ESM1.6 filenames are under development.

All information contained in filenames will be present in file metadata attributes.

1.2 File content

Output files will be NetCDF4 files with data variables compressed using `zlib` with deflate level of at least 1 and shuffle enabled. If a compression level greater than 1 is used please consider the benefit of improved compression ratios against cost of increased compression/decompression times.

Where possible files will conform to the CF metadata conventions (version 1.11) and use the CF Convention Standard Name Table.

For ACCESS-ESM1.6 every file will contain a single data variable/field from a single simulation.

1.3 Metadata Attributes

1.3.1 Global Attributes

Global attributes provide information on the context for the data such as the creation time, experiment it is part of, or science configurations used. All the attributes in the table below are recommended but not all are required, see the `Required` column, and attributes not specified are permitted. Attributes are sorted alphabetically by name.

For any given experiment run, the combination of `model` and `model_version` identify the code used to generate the data. `experiment_repo` and `run_id` identify a specific commit in the repository containing the configuration used.

Title	Description	Type	Examples	Rules	Required
base_configuration	Configuration modified for experiment, see configs repo: https://github.com/ACCESS-NRI/access-esm1.6-configs	string	release-preindustrial+concentrations-2.0		Yes
contact	Email address or other contact details for who to contact regarding this data.	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • access.nri@anu.edu.au • John Smith (john.smith@email.com) 		Yes
Conventions	Convention(s) used with their versions, as a comma separated list	string	CF-1.11,ACDD-1.3		Yes
data_specification	Version of this data specification used to generate the data	string	ACCESS Output Data Specification v2-1-0 XX.XXXX/zenodo.XXXXX		Yes
date_created	Date and time the file was created. Follow ISO 8601, i.e. 'YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ'	string	2025-10-07T11:10:00Z	Must match regex: <code>^\d{4}-(1[012] 0[1-9])-(3[01] [12][0-9])0[1-9]T([01][0-9] 2[0-3]):[0-5][0-9]:[0-5][0-9]Z\$</code>	Yes
date_metadata_modified	Date and time the metadata for this file was last modified. Note that this applied just to the metadata, not the data. Follow ISO 8601, i.e. 'YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ'	string	2025-10-07T11:10:00Z	Must match regex: <code>^\d{4}-(1[012] 0[1-9])-(3[01] [12][0-9])0[1-9]T([01][0-9] 2[0-3]):[0-5][0-9]:[0-5][0-9]Z\$</code>	No
date_modified	Date and time the data for this file was last modified. Note that this applied just to the data, not the metadata. Follow ISO 8601, i.e. 'YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ'	string	2025-10-07T11:10:00Z	Must match regex: <code>^\d{4}-(1[012] 0[1-9])-(3[01] [12][0-9])0[1-9]T([01][0-9] 2[0-3]):[0-5][0-9]:[0-5][0-9]Z\$</code>	No
experiment_repo	Git repository URL that describes the experiment	string	https://github.com/ACCESS-Community-Hub/access-esm1.6-dev-experiments		Yes
experiment_uuid	The experiment UUID generated by Payu. Note: this may be the same as id.	string	698E600B-BECF-4CBA-994F-A663A22FCDDF		Yes

Title	Description	Type	Examples	Rules	Required
frequency	Sampling frequency of the data	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12hr • 1day • 1yr 	Must match one of these regex: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ^fx\$ • ^subhr\$ • ^\d+min\$ • ^\d+hr\$ • ^\d+day\$ • ^\d+mon\$ • ^\d+yr\$ • ^\d+dec\$ 	Yes
geospatial_lat_max	Specifies the northernmost latitude covered by the dataset. Units should be "degrees North".	number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 90 • 12.98 		Yes
geospatial_lat_min	Specifies the southernmost latitude covered by the dataset. Units should be "degrees North".	number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -90 • -57.97 		Yes
geospatial_lat_units	Units for the latitude axis described in "geospatial_lat_min" and "geospatial_lat_max" attributes. These should be "degrees_north".	string	degrees_north		No

Title	Description	Type	Examples	Rules	Required
geospatial_lon_max	Specifies the easternmost longitude covered by the dataset. Units should be "degrees East". Cases where geospatial_lon_min is greater than geospatial_lon_max indicate the bounding box extends from geospatial_lon_max, through the longitude range discontinuity meridian (e.g. the antimeridian for -180:180 values ranges) to geospatial_lon_min; for example, geospatial_lon_min=170 and geospatial_lon_max=-175 incorporates 15 degrees of longitude (ranges 170 to 180 and -180 to -175).	number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 180 • -152.61 		Yes
geospatial_lon_min	Specifies the westernmost longitude covered by the dataset. Units should be "degrees East". See also geospatial_lon_max.	number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -180 • 88.48 		Yes
geospatial_lon_units	Units for the longitude axis described in "geospatial_lon_min" and "geospatial_lon_max" attributes. These should be "degrees_east".	string	degrees_east		No
grid	Brief description of output grid characteristics or reference to grid specification. Should be included if the grid is not defined by the dimensions in the file.	string			No

Title	Description	Type	Examples	Rules	Required
license	Information on the license for the data to ensure all users have access to the terms of use. Use SPDX license identifiers where possible. The default license for ACCESS-NRI is CC-BY-4.0, users should change as needed.	string	CC-BY-4.0		Yes
model	Name of the model used to create the data	string	ACCESS-ESM1.6		Yes
model_version	Version of the model used to create the data. Please note here if the model has been modified from an official release, ideally with links to the changes.	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2025.06.001 • 2025.06.001 (modified by John Smith, [link to repo/paper describing modifications]) 		Yes
realm	Realm where the data variable is defined	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • atmos • landIce 	Must be one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • aerosol • atmos • atmosChem • land • landIce • none • ocean • ocnBgchem • sealce • unknown 	Yes
run_id	Git hash for the commit associated with the experiment run	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3a38fe4 • 3a38fe435e156700ab649c4921e99f7c68a168bc 		Yes
title	Name of the dataset. Typically following the Payu naming scheme detailed here - https://payu.readthedocs.io/en/stable/usage.html#experiment-names	string	my_expt-perturb-416af8c6		Yes

Title	Description	Type	Examples	Rules	Required
variable_id	A list of short variable names, separated by commas, for the data variable/s that appear in this file (e.g. tas for surface temperature but not time/latitude/longitude). These names should match the netCDF variable names.	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tas • huss • uas,vas 		No

1.3.2 Variable Attributes

Variable attributes provide information on the data variable such as the units used, `standard_name`, or `cell_methods` used to generate the data. In netCDF files there can be multiple coordinate variables such as `time`, `latitude`, or `time_bnds` and the main output field variable of which there should be only one. Where possible variables and their attributes should follow CF-v1.11 conventions.

Title	Description	Type	Examples
cell_methods	A string comprising a list of space-separated pairs, "name:method", which indicate that for axis "name" the values representing the fields have been determined by "method".	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time: point • time: mean (interval: 1 hour) • time: maximum (interval: 1D) time: mean (interval: 1M)
long_name	A long descriptive name which may, for example, be used for labelling plots.	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Near-Surface Air Temperature • latitude • Potential Evapotranspiration
standard_name	Where possible use the CF standard_name of the variable, otherwise use a unique short phrase separated by underscores to describe the variable.	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • air_pressure_at_sea_level • latitude • water_potential_evaporation_flux
units	The units of measurement for the variable	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K • m-2 s-1

1.4 `time` and `time_bnds`

Variables describing the time dimension must be named `time` and have the following metadata:

Title	Description	Type	Examples	Required
axis	Must have the value 'T'	string	T	Yes
bounds	Must have the value 'time_bnds'	string	time_bnds	No
calendar	Calendar defines the set of valid datetimes and their order. Follows the CF-Convention names using lower-case strings. It is recommended that "proleptic_gregorian" is used for data with leap days and "no_leap"/"365_day" for data without leap days.	string		Yes
long_name	Must have the value 'time'	string	time	Yes
standard_name	Must have the value 'time'	string	time	Yes
units	Units for time should be given as "days since X" where X is a date (yyyy-mm-dd) or a datetime (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM or yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM:SS)	string	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • days since 0001-01-01 00:00:00 • days since 0001-01-01 00:00 • days since 1970-01-01 • days since -5000-12-25 	Yes

Where possible, `time` variables will have their boundaries described by a `time_bnds` variable. The `time_bnds` variable itself will have no attributes.

1.5 Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the specifications and conventions we have used and consulted to construct this specification and the tremendous work of their authors:

- [CMIP6](#)
- [CORDEX](#)
- [ACDD](#)